

**A REVIEW OF PREVENTIVE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF MONKEYPOX W.S.R.
TO MASURIKA****Anjali Mandloi¹, Dinesh Vijaywargiya², R. K. Pati³, Rohit Ambodiya⁴**

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ABSTRACT

Skin diseases are considered a serious health problem. Almost all skin problems in *Ayurveda* are explained by the wide term "*Kushtha*". *Madhava Nidana* is an ancient Ayurvedic text on diagnostics written by *Madhava-kara* (700-800 AD). *Madhavakara* was the first author to give an independent disease status along with a detailed description of *Masurika* in *Masurika Nidana* chapter of the *Madhava Nidana*. *Masurika* can be correlated with small pox, which is one type of *kshudra Kushtha* as described in the classics.^[1] Small pox caused by variola virus, Orthopoxgenus. It is a serious, highly contagious and sometimes fatal disease. Mpox, formerly called monkey-pox, is a rare disease similar to smallpox caused by a virus. Common symptoms of mpox are a skin rash or mucosal lesions which can last 2-4 weeks accompanied by fever, headache, muscle aches, back pain, low energy and swollen lymph nodes. The exploration of herbs and their phytochemical properties for potential therapeutic effects against monkey-pox is a growing area of interest. While research specifically targeting monkeypox is limited, certain herbs traditionally known for their antiviral, immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective, and anti-inflammatory properties could be beneficial based on their general pharmacological activities.

KEYWORD'S: *Masurika*, MONKEYPOX, smallpox, Orthopox genus, *kshudra Kushtha*, pharmacological activities of *Ayurveda herbs*.

INTRODUCTION

Skin diseases are considered a serious health problem. Almost all skin problems in *Ayurveda* are explained by the wide term "*Kushtha*".

Madhavakara was the first author to give an independent disease status along with a detailed description of *Masurika* in *Masurika Nidana* chapter of the *Madhava Nidana*.

Masurika can be correlated with small pox, which is one type of *kshudra Kushtha* as described in the classics. Excessive and/or regular consumption of food items such as spicy (*Katu*), sour (*Amla*), salty (*Lavana*), alkaline or

caustic (*Kshara*), incompatible diet (*Viruddha*), high meal frequency/day (*Adhyashana*), spoiled or contaminated food (*Dushta*); excessive consumption of common beans or legumes (*Nishpava*) and green leafy vegetables (*Shaaka*); contaminated or polluted (*Pradushta*) air (*Pawana*) and water (*Udaka*) and particular cities or states or countries (*Deshe*) affected by malevolent spirits (*Krura Grahekshnat*) causes vitiation of bodily humors (*Doshas*) and blood (*Dushta Rakta*) that ultimately leads to the manifestation of skin eruptions (*Pidaka*) similar to that of lentils (*Masura*) in size, shape, and color (*Akrti* and *Samsthana*).

Small pox caused by variola virus, Orthopox genus. It is

a serious, highly contagious and sometimes fatal death. Mpox, formerly called monkey-pox, is a rare disease similar to smallpox caused by a virus. Common symptoms of mpox are a skin rash or mucosal lesions which can last 2-4 weeks accompanied by fever, headache, muscle ach, back pain, low energy and

swollen lymph nodes.

The exploration of herbs and their phytochemical properties for potential therapeutic effects against monkey-pox is a growing area of interest.

METHODOLOGY AYURVEDA VIEW

Drug name	Botanical name	Chemical composition	Indication
Giloy/Guduchi	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Tinosporidine, Diterpenoid,	<i>Tridoshara, daha-prashamana, dipaniya, Kandughna, jwara-hara</i>
Chirayta/Kirat-tikta	<i>Swertia chirayata</i>	Gentiopiricin, mangiferin, Swertinin, kairatenol	Kapha-pittahara, Dahahara, vranahara, kushtahara
Vasa	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Adhatodic acid, vasicinine, Luteolin	kapharghna, chedana, kaphapittahara, kushthahara, jwarghna, chedana, krimighna
Kutki/chakrangi	<i>Picrorrhiza Kurroa</i>	Kutkiol, apocyanin, D-mannitol, kutkisterol, phenol glucosides	<i>Kapha-pittahara, kushthaghna, bhedana, lekhana,</i>

Drug name	Neem
Botanical name	<i>Azadiracta indica</i>
Chemical composition	Mimbinin(0.01%), mimbosterol(0.03%), Mimbinin(0.01%), mimbosterol, (0.03%),
Indication	<i>Kapha-pittahara, vranahara, jwarhara, krumihara, dipana</i>

Drug name	Kanchnar
Botanical name	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>
Chemical composition	Bark-tannin, Stem - bita sitosterol, lupeol etc.
Indication	<i>Kapha-pittahara, Sothahara, lekhana, dipana, Krimighna, Twagadoshahara, Gandamalanasak</i>

Drug name	Patola
Botanical name	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>
Chemical composition	Nicotinic acid, vit A, Riboflavin, Thimine
Indication	<i>Kapha-pittahara, Deepana, krimighna, pachana</i>

Drug name	Patha
Botanical name	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>
Chemical composition	Cycleanine, hayatidin, hayatinin
Indication	<i>Vata-kaphahara, Visaghna, Kushthaghna</i>

Drug name	Haridra
Botanical name	<i>Curcuma longa</i>
Chemical composition	Curcumene, Curcone, cineole camphene etc.
Indication	<i>Kapha-vatahara, Vishaghna, lekhana, Krimighna, Varnya Kusthaghna</i>

Drug name	Yasti-madhu
Botanical name	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
Chemical composition	Glabrane, glycyrrhizin, Glabranine, liquiritic acid
Indication	<i>Tridoshahara, Vednahara</i>

DISCUSSION

In Ayurveda, herbs like *Yashtimadhu*, *Guduchi*, *Haridra*

& *kutki* are used as blood-purifying agents which is useful to clear the infection from the body. It also helps

to cleanse the lymphatic system. *Ayurvedic* treatment of smallpox includes use of herbs, topical formulations, as well as oral formulations to reduce itching, boil formation & fevers. These formulations have blood purifying, immunity-enhancing properties so, it is helpful to achieve a speedy recovery of mpox patient.

CONCLUSION

According to the literature mentioned above, both *Ayurveda* and modern medicine offer both curative and preventive treatments. *Ayurveda* claims that *grahadosha* is a contributing element to this illness, while modern theory holds that viruses are to blame. It is evident from studying *Ayurvedic* literature that *shitala matas prakop*, vitiation of *tridoshas*, and *grahadosha* are the causes of *masurika/lagu masurika*. *Ayurvedic* medications can also cure all forms of this illness. Modern literature claims that the varicella virus causes Small pox, which can be effectively prevented by vaccination and treated with contemporary medications.

Thus, based on the study's above explanation, we can say that both pathies are equally effective in treating and preventing chickenpox, also known as *Masurika/Laghu Masurika*.

While these herbs have demonstrated various pharmacological activities that could theoretically support the immune system and combat viral infections, specific research on their effectiveness against monkeypox is still needed. It's crucial to approach herbal remedies with caution and consult healthcare professionals before using them, especially in the context of infectious diseases.

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